

Applying steady state treatment and assuming $K_2 \ll K_{-1}$, the rate of reaction is given by the equation,

$$-\frac{d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]}{dt} = \frac{K_{eq} \cdot K_2 K_3 [\text{Alkanal}][\text{OH}^-][\text{O}_8^{\text{VIII}}]}{K_{-2}}$$

The rate equation satisfactorily explains all the observed kinetic features except the fractional order with respect to $[\text{OH}^-]$, an observation similar to the oxidation of aromatic aldehydes⁴⁻⁶ by permanganate. The fractional order with respect to hydroxyl ion concentration suggests a negative centre at the site of attack or a free radical. A negative acrylamide test excludes the possibility of free radical, thus involvement of negative centres at the site of attack, *i.e.* mono-anion of the alkanal hydrate is the only possibility.

The fractional order with respect to alkali shows that there are two reactive species, *i.e.* alkanal hydrate and anion of the hydrate as indicated by the above equation.

The first order rate constant $K_2/[\text{substrate}]$, for methanal, ethanal, propanal and n-butanal are respectively 3.24, 2.20, 3.50 and $1.69 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$, which shows that the substituted alkanals with electron donating substituents react faster than ethanal (substituted).

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Studies on Aminoacetamides. Part-I. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of *p,p'*-Bis(arylamidomethylamino)diphenylsulphones

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AMINOACETAMIDE derivatives have been found to possess a wide variety of physiological activities¹⁻⁹. Keeping this in view, some new amino-

acetamide derivatives of type 1 were synthesised by condensing 4,4'-diaminodiphenylsulphone with monochloromethyl acetate and then treated with sodium hydroxide to get *p,p'*-bis(carboxymethylamino)diphenylsulphone. This was then condensed with thionyl chloride and different aromatic amines. The compounds were characterised on the basis of their elemental analyses and spectroscopic data. The products were screened for their antimicrobial activity.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu 435 spectrophotometer. Pmr spectra (DMSO-*d*₆) were recorded on a EM 360 (60 MHz) spectrometer.

p,p'-Bis (carbmethoxymethylamino) diphenylsulphone : 4,4'-Diaminodiphenylsulphone (0.01 mol) dissolved in dimethylformamide (30 ml) was added to monochloromethyl acetate (0.02 mol) and refluxed for 3 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from methanol, (68%), m.p. 156° (Found : C, 55.05 ; H, 5.04 ; N, 7.10. C₁₈H₂₀N₂O₆S calcd for : C, 55.10 ; N, 7.14%).

p,p'-Bis (carboxymethylamino) diphenylsulphone : A mixture of *p,p'*-bis(carbomethoxymethylamino)-diphenylsulphone (0.01 mol) and dilute sodium hydroxide (10 ml) was refluxed for 1.5 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from methanol, (62%), m.p. 98° (Found : C, 52.70 ; H, 4.32 ; N, 7.63. C₁₆H₁₆N₂O₆S calcd. for : C, 52.74 ; H, 4.39 ; N, 7.69%).

p,p'-Bis (phenylamidomethylamino) diphenylsulphone : A mixture of *p,p'*-bis(carboxymethylamino)-diphenylsulphone (0.01 mol) dissolved in dioxane (10 ml) and thionyl chloride (0.02 mol) was refluxed for 6 h. Excess of thionyl chloride was removed by distillation. The product obtained was refluxed with aniline and 2-3 drops of pyridine using dioxane (10 ml) as solvent for a further 3 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from methanol. (78%), m.p. > 360° (Found : C, 63.33 ; H, 5.02 ; N, 10.85. C₂₈H₂₈N₄O₄S calcd. for : C, 63.36 ; H, 5.05 ; N, 10.89%) ; ν_{max} (KBr) 1 375 (SO₂ sym. str.), 1 150 (SO₂ sym. str.), 3 325 (NH str.), 1 640 (C=O str.), 1 520 (NH def. +C-N str.) and 1 300 cm⁻¹ (NH def. +C-N str.) ; δ (TMS ; DMSO-*d*₆) 2.68 (6H, s, CH₃), 3.5 (4H, s, CH₂), 4.2 (4H, s, NH) and 7.9-6.6 (16H, m, Ar-H).

Similarly, other aminoacetamide derivatives were prepared. The physical data are recorded in Table 1.

Antimicrobial activity : Aminoacetamide derivatives were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activity using cup-plate method⁹. The testing was carried out at a concentration of 100 μg using

NOTES

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY DATA OF *p,p'*-BIS(ARYLAMIDOMETHYLAMINO)DIPHENYLSULPHONES

R	Mol. formula	M p. °C	Yield %	Nitrogen % : Found/(Calcd.)
Phenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₄ S	360	82	10.85 (10.89)
<i>o</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₄ S	178	63	10.30 (10.33)
<i>m</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₄ S	182	77	10.28 (10.28)
<i>p</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₄ S	197	55	10.32 (10.32)
<i>o</i> -Anisyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₆ S	298	56	9.72 (9.75)
<i>m</i> -Anisyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₆ S	320	66	9.80 (9.84)
<i>p</i> -Anisyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₆ S	215	75	9.75 (9.70)
<i>o</i> -Carboxyphenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₆ S	325	88	9.30 (9.25)
<i>m</i> -Carboxyphenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₆ S	330	68	9.26 (9.30)
<i>p</i> -Carboxyphenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₆ S	330	75	9.28 (9.30)
<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₄ Cl ₂ S	128	82	9.55 (9.60)
<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₄ S	205	66	9.58 (9.60)
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₄ S	142	58	9.58 (9.60)
<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₆ S	137	68	13.88 (13.90)
<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₆ S	262	66	13.83 (13.40)
<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₆ S	278	78	13.86 (13.90)
<i>m</i> -Acetylphenyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₆ S	260	73	9.32 (9.36)
<i>p</i> -Acetylphenyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₆ S	320	68	9.30 (9.32)
Benzyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₄ S	360	72	10.80 (10.33)
Naphthyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄ S	190	63	9.10 (9.12)
<i>o</i> -Bromophenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₄ Br ₂ S	225	88	8.32 (8.33)
<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₆ S	205	75	9.24 (9.30)
<i>p</i> -Carbethoxyphenyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₆ S	360	48	8.46 (8.51)
<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₆ S	335	56	10.20 (10.25)
Antipyrin-4-yl	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₄ S	315	73	15.22 (15.25)
Sulphoxyphenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₁₀ S	360	52	8.18 (8.30)

gram-positive bacteria, *i.e.* *Staphylococcus aureus* and *S. citreus*, and gram-negative bacteria, *i.e.* *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella typhosa*. The antifungal testing was carried out against *Aspergillus niger* and *Neurospora cressa*. Most of the compounds showed moderate activity against different strains of bacteria and fungi.

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Studies on 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles. Part-IV. Preparation of 2-Aryl-5-(2',4'-bis-*p*-chlorophenyl-amino-*s*-triazin-6'-ylaminomethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles

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1,3,4-Oxadiazoles are known to exhibit a wide spectrum of physiological properties like anti-tubercular¹, bactericidal^{2,3}, fungicidal⁴, analgesic, antipyretic^{5,6}, hypoglycemic⁷, hypnotic and sedative⁸. *s*-Triazine derivatives have also been reported to possess antiviral⁹, antimalarial^{10,11} and anticancer^{12,13} properties. The present investigation was undertaken with a view to synthesise new derivatives and to screen them for their antimicrobial activity.

Keeping this in view, some new 2,5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles having *s*-triazine moiety have been prepared by the condensation of different aromatic acids with the hydrazide of 2,4-bis-*p*-chlorophenyl-amino-6-carbethoxymethylamino-*s*-triazine in presence of POCl₃ to obtain the 1,3,4-oxadiazoles of type 1.

1; R = Aryl

Experimental

Melting points were determined in capillary tubes using a paraffin-bath and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu-IR-435 spectrophotometer. Pmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) were recorded on a Varian FT-80A spectrophotometer with tetramethylsilane as the internal reference.

2,4-Bis(p-chlorophenylamino)-s-triazin-6-ylamino-acylhydrazide: A mixture of 2,4-bis-*p*-chlorophenyl-amino-6-carbethoxymethylamino-*s*-triazine¹⁴ (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol) in dioxane was refluxed for 6 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from methanol, (85%), m.p. 243° (Found: C, 48.53; H, 3.79; N, 26.35. C₁₇H₁₆ON₈Cl₂ calcd. for: C, 48.8; H, 3.83; N, 26.79%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 400 (NH), 3 350–3 280 (doublet, NH), 1 660 (C=O), 820 (C₃N₃) and 800 cm⁻¹ (C–Cl).

2-Phenyl-5-(2',4'-bis-*p*-chlorophenylamino-*s*-triazin-6'-ylaminomethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole: A mixture of 2,4-bis(*p*-chlorophenylamino)-*s*-triazin-6'-ylamino-acylhydrazide (0.01 mol) and benzoic acid (0.01 mol) in POCl₃ (5 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from methanol, (69%), m.p. > 300° (Found: C, 56.93; H, 3.49; N, 22.11. C₃₄H₁₈ON₈Cl₂ calcd. for: C, 57.14; H, 3.57; N, 22.22%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 350 (NH), 1 570 (C=N), 1 090 (C–O–C), 820 (C₃N₃) and 760 cm⁻¹ (C–Cl); τ (TMS; DMSO-d₆) 1.9–2.8 (12 H, m, Ar–H), 6.7 (s, NH) and 7.2 (2H, s, CH₂).

Similarly, other substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles of the type 1 were prepared by condensation of different aromatic acids with 2,4-bis(*p*-chlorophenylamino)-*s*-triazin-6-ylaminoacylhydrazide. The physical data are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF 2-ARYL-5-(2',4'-BIS-*p*-CHLOROPHENYLAMINO-*s*-TRIAZIN-6'-YLAMINO-METHYL)-1,3,4-OXADIAZOLE*

R	Mol. formula	Yield %	M.p. °C
Phenyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ ON ₈ Cl ₂	75	> 300
<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ ON ₈ Cl ₃	71	> 300
<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ ON ₈ Cl ₃	79	260
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ ON ₈ Cl ₃	60	255
<i>o</i> -Aminophenyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ ON ₈ Cl ₂	63	190
<i>m</i> -Aminophenyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ ON ₈ Cl ₂	68	212
<i>p</i> -Aminophenyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ ON ₈ Cl ₂	71	176
<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₈ Cl ₂	60	219
<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₈ Cl ₂	62	215
Cinnamyl	C ₂₈ H ₁₉ ON ₈ Cl ₂	76	166
<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	C ₂₈ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₈ Cl ₂	59	168d
<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₉ Cl ₂	62	220d
<i>o</i> -Acetoxyphenyl	C ₂₈ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₈ Cl ₂	74	90
2-Hydroxy-3-naphthyl	C ₂₈ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₈ Cl ₂	78	171
2,4-Dihydroxyphenyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₈ Cl ₂	60	217
Benzyl	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ ON ₈ Cl ₂	70	222
3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	C ₂₈ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₈ Cl ₂	75	228d
<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ ON ₈ Cl ₂ Br	76	226
<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ ON ₈ Cl ₂	80	> 300
3-Pyridyl	C ₂₉ H ₂₁ ON ₈ Cl ₂	69	800d
4-Pyridyl	C ₂₉ H ₂₁ ON ₈ Cl ₂	74	161d
3,4,5-Trihydroxyphenyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₈ Cl ₂	67	218

*Satisfactory analyses were obtained.

Antimicrobial activity: The antimicrobial assay was carried out with the compounds (Table 1) using cup-plate¹⁵ method against species of gram-positive bacteria like *Staphylococcus aureus*, *S. citreus*, *S. albus*, gram-negative bacteria like *Escherichia coli* and fungi like *Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium chrysogenum*. The testing was carried out in DMF solution at a concentration of 50 μg when zone of inhibition from 9 to 38 mm were observed depend-